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3 **Good Environmental Status of marine ecosystems: What is it and how do we know**
4 **when we have attained it?**

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26
27 **Abstract**

28 The European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) requires EU Member
29 States (MS) to achieve Good Environmental Status (GEnS) of their seas by 2020. We
30 address the question of what GEnS entails especially with regard to the level at which
31 targets are set (descriptors, criteria, indicators), to scales for assessments (regional, sub-
32 divisions, site-specific), and to difficulties in putting into practice the GEnS concept.
33 We propose a refined and operational definition of GEnS, indicating the data and
34 information needed to all parts of that definition. We indicate the options for
35 determining when GEnS has been met, acknowledge the data and information needs for
36 each option, and recommend a combination of existing quantitative targets and expert
37 judgement. We think that the MSFD implementation needs to be less complex than
38 shown for other similar directives, can be based largely on existing data and can be
39 centred on the activities of the Regional Seas Conventions.

40

41 **Key words:** Assessment; Good Environmental Status; descriptors; indicators;

42 integration; Marine Strategy Framework Directive

43 **Introduction**

44 Marine waters have traditionally been used by society for different activities (e.g.
45 fishing, aquaculture, shipping, tourism, discharges from agriculture and urban areas).
46 Currently, new activities are being developed or increasing (e.g. renewable energies,
47 extraction of minerals, etc.), and thus competing for space with traditional uses, causing
48 many spatial conflicts and increasing human impacts on marine ecosystems (Ban and
49 Alder, 2008; Halpern *et al.*, 2008). While the legal framework for ‘marine spatial
50 planning and coastal development’ is relatively new (Ehler and Douvere, 2009;
51 European Commission, 2013), most of the legislation to protect, conserve or enhance
52 marine ecosystems is based upon the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
53 (UNCLOS, 1982).

54 In Europe, there are two main Directives focusing on these topics: (i) the Water
55 Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC; European Commission, 2000), which, covers
56 transitional and coastal waters up to 1 nm from the continental baseline, and (ii) the
57 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC; European Commission,
58 2008), covering all marine waters up to the limit of the Exclusive Economic Zone
59 (EEZ) and extended continental shelf. In addition, there is a proposed Directive for
60 Maritime Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Management (European Commission,
61 2013) which will integrate management and planning.

62 Both the existing Directives try to ensure that the marine use is compatible with
63 the conservation of ecosystems and the maintenance of the good status of waters,
64 habitats and resources. The MSFD aims to achieve or maintain ‘good environmental
65 status’ (GEnS) in marine waters, by 2020 (European Commission, 2008), whilst the
66 WFD aims to achieve ‘good ecological status’ (GEcS) in transitional and coastal waters,
67 by 2015. Following the recommendation from Mee *et al.* (2008), we use the GEnS and
68 GEcS acronyms because the meaning of ‘environmental’ and ‘ecological’ is different

69 (see Borja *et al.* (2010), for differences between both concepts), implying a different
70 emphasis between these two major pieces of legislation.

71 It has been argued that GEcS, as required by the WFD, focuses more on
72 ecological structure, i.e. at a given time the abundance, presence, cover, etc., of
73 ecological components, referred to as biological quality elements (Heiskanen *et al.*,
74 2004; Borja *et al.*, 2010), i.e. phytoplankton, macrophytes, macroinvertebrates and fish
75 (the latter not in marine waters). In turn, the concept of environmental status, as defined
76 by the MSFD, takes into account the structure, function and processes of marine
77 ecosystems, bringing together natural physical, chemical, physiographic, geographic
78 and climatic factors, and integrates these conditions with anthropogenic impacts and
79 activities carried out in the area of concern (European Commission, 2008). Hence, it has
80 been argued that, in using wider descriptors which relate to pressures, the MSFD
81 provides a functional approach to measuring ecosystem health, where ‘functional’ refers
82 to rate (i.e. time-dependent) processes (Borja *et al.*, 2010).

83 According to the MSFD, the environmental status is defined by 11 descriptors,
84 and forms a proposed set of 29 associated criteria and 56 indicators that include
85 biological, physico-chemical indicators as well as pressure indicators—including
86 hazardous substances, hydrological alterations, litter and noise, and biological
87 disturbance such as introduction of non-indigenous species (Cardoso *et al.*, 2010;
88 European Commission, 2010) (Table 1). Following the implementation schedule of the
89 MSFD, EU Member States (MS) started to assess the environmental status of their
90 marine waters in 2012. This assessment should be carried out in an integrative way,
91 including measurement of many ecosystem components together with physicochemical
92 parameters and elements of pollution (Borja *et al.*, 2009). However, in most countries,
93 the precise means of implementing the MSFD are yet unclear. In most cases MS are

94 focussing on individual descriptors and then criteria and indicators within the
95 descriptors, with apparently little or no attention being paid to the means of combining
96 the indicators, criteria and descriptors into a holistic assessment of the environmental
97 status (http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/public-consultation/index_en.htm).
98 Although several attempts have been made to assess the environmental status of marine
99 waters in an integrative manner (HELCOM, 2010; Borja *et al.*, 2011), there are still
100 significant gaps regarding: (i) the understanding of marine ecosystems and their
101 responses to human activities, including climate change; (ii) the baseline knowledge
102 required to define GEnS in an adequate and operational way; (iii) the meaning of GEnS
103 itself, and (iv) the identification, measurement and weighting of the components of the
104 different indicators. For example, one indicator of biodiversity is the distribution range
105 of species. However, the questions on how many species should be taken into account,
106 whether all species are equally important, whether they should be considered as groups
107 or as species and on a seasonal or annual basis, are yet to be answered (Borja *et al.*,
108 2010).

109 To assist MS in determining GEnS, several principles were highlighted in a
110 Common Understanding document (Claussen *et al.*, 2011). However, we contend that
111 these do not provide an operational approach nor tackle the fundamental question of
112 how to integrate all the aspects of assessment within and among marine areas. Here we
113 highlight those principles that could help to answer two main questions: what is GEnS
114 and how do we know when it is attained? In particular, we focus on: (i) the conceptual
115 definition of GEnS and related problems (e.g. the different steps for selecting
116 criteria/indicators and the proposal of minimum common approaches); (ii) the role of
117 setting of targets to determine GEnS; (iii) the existing approaches for integrating

118 assessment results, from the indicator level up to the level of GEnS of a marine area,
119 and (iv) an operational definition of GEnS, with the challenges for deriving and using it.

120

121 **Current definition of Good Environmental Status and associated problems**

122 The MSFD defines GEnS as “*the environmental status of marine waters where*
123 *these provide ecologically diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are intrinsically*
124 *clean, healthy and productive, and the use of the marine environment is at a level that is*
125 *sustainable, thus safeguarding the potential for uses and activities by current and future*
126 *generations*” (European Commission, 2008). Hence, this implicitly requires ecosystem
127 services and societal benefits to be delivered (Atkins *et al.*, 2011a, b) even though the
128 descriptors and their proposed criteria do not mention these aspects.

129 The concept of environmental status and the normative definitions of GEnS
130 relate to the structure and successful functioning of ecosystems which allow them to
131 maintain their resilience to human-induced environmental change (Elliott *et al.*, 2007).
132 This means that marine species and habitats are protected, human-induced decline of
133 biodiversity is prevented, and diverse biological components are in balance. In addition,
134 hydrographical, physical and chemical properties of the ecosystems, including those
135 which result from human activities, support the ecosystems as described above. Finally,
136 anthropogenic inputs of substances and energy, including noise, into the marine
137 environment do not cause significant adverse effects to marine environment and allow
138 ecosystem services and societal benefits to be maintained and delivered (Atkins *et al.*,
139 2011a, b). There is, however, little understanding of what to consider as a meaningful
140 quantitative definition of GEnS for a marine area, despite the stipulation in the MSFD
141 that GEnS is an expression of the desired condition of the environment.

142 Background work to define GEnS at individual descriptor level was undertaken
143 by different Task Groups for 10 out of the 11 descriptors (Table 2): biodiversity
144 (Cochrane *et al.*, 2010); non-indigenous species (Olenin *et al.*, 2010); exploited fish
145 (Piet *et al.*, 2010); food-webs (Rogers *et al.*, 2010); human-induced eutrophication
146 (Ferreira *et al.*, 2010); seafloor integrity (Rice *et al.*, 2010); contaminants (Law *et al.*,
147 2010; Swartenbroux *et al.*, 2010); litter (Galgani *et al.*, 2010) and noise (Tasker *et al.*,
148 2010). The remaining descriptor, alterations of hydrographical conditions, was
149 addressed in a more general way. For some descriptors, the Task Group report included
150 a clearer definition of GEnS than for others (Table 2). This lack of clarity means that
151 cross-border harmonisation is needed to ensure that environmental status does not
152 change abruptly at the maritime boundary of two states.

153 The Commission (COM) Decision 2010/477/EU on criteria and methodological
154 standards on good environmental status of marine waters, supported by the documents
155 prepared by the Working Groups, provided a range of criteria and indicators based on
156 which GEnS should be defined. This Decision acknowledges that the application of
157 criteria and identification of indicators should take into account the essential features
158 and characteristics, pressures and impacts identified by MS during the initial assessment
159 of the marine waters (MSFD Article 8, Annex I and III). It gives flexibility for MS to
160 select those criteria and associated indicators that address the most important impacts
161 and threats to a particular marine ecosystem. It also allows for the use of limited
162 criteria/indicators across a wide marine area, leaving the application of additional
163 criteria/indicators to specific subareas. Consequently, we emphasise that the central task
164 for implementing the MSFD is to determine how the many different criteria/indicators
165 should be combined into an integrative assessment framework.

166 Although the latest available Common Understanding document (Claussen *et al.*,
167 2011), drafted by a group assigned to develop a common understanding of the main
168 normative concepts of the MSFD, mentions that “*assessments following the first MSFD*
169 *cycle should move towards full consideration of the relevant criteria and indicators as*
170 *laid down in COM Decision 2010/477/EU*”, it is still unclear if this requires ‘full’ use of
171 the criteria and indicators as laid down in the COM Decision or only those ‘relevant’ to
172 each marine region. This ambiguity is likely to lead to different approaches (and hence
173 possible confusion) within and between MS, and should be accounted for in any
174 proposal for integrating at the level of criteria and indicators. Therefore, although the
175 choice of criteria/indicators and aggregation rules are the responsibility of MS,
176 coherence of frameworks within the different marine regions or sub-regions and across
177 the Community should be ensured. Accordingly, we question whether minimum
178 requirements should be proposed, and if so, at which level should those minima be set:
179 indicators, criteria or descriptors.

180

181 **The role of setting targets in quantifying Good Environmental Status**

182 After agreeing on what to include for definition of GEnS, the next question, if
183 we are to implement it, would be: on which level do we define it and how do we
184 quantify it? The MS Initial Assessments (available at
185 http://cdr.eionet.europa.eu/recent_etc?RA_ID=608) made it clear that these were
186 ambiguous steps, since both GEnS and Environmental Targets have been defined and
187 set at different levels across MS, from descriptor level to indicator level. Hence, we
188 question the implications of this for GEnS comparability.

189 Many environmental initiatives worldwide, and especially European Directives,
190 have the fundamental requirement for an authority to determine whether an

191 area/ecological component/habitat is as expected given the prevailing environmental
192 conditions and, if not and the changes are due to human activities, then which actions
193 are required to remediate any problems. Hence, assessing the current environmental
194 status requires a comparison between an expected/usual/normal state and an impacted
195 one. Thus, it is necessary to determine a reference/baseline/threshold/trigger condition
196 against which the actual or potentially changed situation can be compared (Borja *et al.*,
197 2012). Therefore by definition, the determination of good status implies a condition
198 which has been or can be compared against that anthropogenically-altered state. For
199 example, the WFD indicates that there are four ways of determining that reference
200 condition: (i) to find an area similar to the one under study, but without the pressures
201 (*de facto*, a control area); (ii) to hindcast to a time before pressures exerted an influence;
202 (iii) to numerically model an unimpacted condition for comparison, and, if none of these
203 are possible, (iv) to use expert judgement (Hering *et al.*, 2010). Each of these
204 alternatives poses challenges: (i) the unavailability or difficulty of finding unimpacted
205 conditions, especially in the highly developed areas or within eco-regions; (ii) the
206 question of the baseline conditions for hindcasting (and the basis that some unimpacted
207 prior utopia may be unattainable); (iii) the uncertainty or unavailability of numerical
208 models for unbounded marine areas or moving baselines (caused by climate change),
209 and (iv) the perceived reluctance to rely on expert judgement if there is the likelihood of
210 any legal challenge to management mechanisms such as sanctions to industries likely to
211 impact an area (Duarte *et al.*, 2009; Carstensen *et al.*, 2011; Borja *et al.*, 2012).

212 It is axiomatic that ‘you cannot manage without measurement’ and so numerical
213 targets are central in determining whether MS succeed or fail to attain GEnS (Borja *et*
214 *al.*, 2012). The description of GEnS and the establishment of environmental targets
215 (under Articles 9 and 10 of the MSFD, respectively) need a clear understanding for

216 making this GEnS assessment operational. Claussen *et al.* (2011) suggest that the
217 MSFD depends on measurable environmental targets and thus is linked to relevant
218 indicators. Furthermore, they expect that the indicators and environmental targets will
219 be related to the 11 Descriptors and thus directly linked to the marine environmental
220 pressures as indicated in the Annex III of the MSFD. Most importantly they suggest that
221 “... to articulate quantitatively what GES looks like and/or set appropriate
222 environmental targets it will be necessary to define for each of the criteria and, where
223 appropriate, the indicators in COM Decision 2010/477/EU, environmental boundaries
224 or thresholds above or below which GES is considered to have been met. ... To that
225 effect, a boundary between success and failure to achieve or maintain GES should be
226 established. Thresholds/levels/limits in this sense represent that boundary between an
227 acceptable and unacceptable status”.

228 These comments indicate the central problem being addressed here – that in the
229 discussions of the Common Implementation Strategy of the MSFD, GEnS is still
230 contemplated as a combination, as yet undefined, of indicators, targets, thresholds,
231 levels, limits, criteria, and descriptors. Hence, we need to question whether these
232 “environmental thresholds/levels/limits” are equivalent to environmental targets and, if
233 so, does this mean we would have GEnS/non-GEnS at indicator level. It is therefore
234 necessary to clarify whether an ‘Environmental Target’, as described in Art.10 of the
235 MSFD, is equivalent to an ‘Environmental threshold/level/limit’ proposed at the level of
236 indicators to make them operational by monitoring the changes in attributes (Claussen
237 *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, if they are, how do these environmental targets at the
238 indicator level relate to a broader GEnS description for any given marine region? Annex
239 IV of the MSFD presents the term Environmental Target as a far more complex and

240 integrative concept (Figure 1) that is unlikely to be set at the indicator level or informed
241 effectively by a single indicator.

242 Claussen *et al.* (2011) recognize four types of environmental targets: pressure-,
243 state-, impact-based- and operational targets whose adequacy is largely dependent on
244 the robustness of the evidence available and the nature of any Descriptor. However,
245 their examples indicate that the type of targets differ essentially according to how the
246 target is expressed (as state indicators, identified pressures, or impacts on biodiversity
247 components) rather than in the approaches used to measure achievement of targets (see
248 examples in Claussen *et al.*, 2011).

249

250 **Integration of the assessments: from indicator level up to the level of GEnS**

251 After setting reference values for the indicators, and determining the status of
252 individual indicators and descriptors, a new problem emerges when attempting to
253 integrate all this information into a unique status assessment. Whereas the WFD uses
254 the so-called rule ‘one out, all out’ (OOAO), which means that the element with the
255 worst status determines the global status and hence is regarded as a precautionary level,
256 no specific rule has yet been proposed for the MSFD. However, when proposing
257 aggregation rules, the Task Groups for the implementation of the MSFD deconstructed
258 the ecosystem into ‘descriptor indicators’ and then recombined them to give a pass/fail
259 for the GEnS, using in four of the cases the OOAO principle (Table 2). We take the
260 view that such a ‘deconstructive structural approach’ makes large assumptions about the
261 functioning of the system and does not consider the weighting of the different indicators
262 and descriptors (Borja *et al.*, 2010). It implies that recombining a set of structural
263 attributes gives an accurate representation of the ecosystem functioning.

264 Our detailed analysis of the work carried out by the descriptor-specific working
265 groups suggests there has been a lot of initial activity, but little attention was paid to
266 how the data/information will eventually be used. Despite their importance,
267 combination rules for the MSFD descriptors and indicators were excluded from the
268 remit of the Task Groups; in our view, an omission which needs to be addressed. For
269 example, if the OOA principle was to be applied to the 11 descriptors and 56
270 indicators, the probability to fail one or more indicators, even through analytical error,
271 would be very high at any studied location, as demonstrated for the WFD with fewer
272 components, the 5 biological quality elements (Borja and Rodríguez, 2010). This is
273 especially problematical when different elements address the same pressure (Caroni *et*
274 *al.*, 2013) which, if both are combined, leads to ‘double-counting’ and thus an over-
275 emphasis on the resulting status. Although Annex 1 of the MSFD describes the GEnS
276 individually for each of the 11 descriptors, this does not imply the ability to have GEnS
277 at the level of all the descriptors, nor does it mean that each descriptor should
278 necessarily be graded individually in a binary way (i.e. good or not good environmental
279 status). For example, the HELCOM (2010) tool for assessment of ‘ecosystem health’ (in
280 practice equivalent to GEnS) groups indicators into 3 categories: biology, hazardous
281 substances, and supporting indicators; applying then the OOA rule at the 3 category
282 level. Hence, reducing the MSFD descriptors to 3 groups, and then using the OOA
283 approach for those groups, may be a pragmatic compromise which minimises the
284 probability of failure, due to analytical errors or statistical chance, while still giving one
285 overall assessment of GEnS. This is analogous to the Environmental Integrative
286 Indicator (EII) approach of Aubry and Elliott (2006) in which 27 indicators were
287 grouped and weighted into 3 EII.

288 The integration issue is further complicated by the fact that some of the
289 descriptors function as pressures for other descriptors; e.g. alien species can be a threat
290 to biodiversity and food web functioning; alterations in the hydrological regime can be a
291 threat to seafloor integrity. Thus, we suggest that the 11 descriptors are hierarchical and
292 do not have an equal weighting when assessing the overall GEnS (Borja *et al.*, 2010).
293 We further suggest that we take the philosophical view that for the descriptor
294 Biodiversity to be fulfilled requires all others to be met and similarly if one of the
295 stressor or pressure-related descriptors (e.g. energy including noise) fails then by
296 definition the biodiversity will be adversely affected.

297 In addition to this problem of aggregating indicators and descriptors, whilst the
298 WFD centres on quality assessments within a small area, albeit extrapolated to a water
299 body (Hering *et al.*, 2010), the MSFD requires MS to integrate and geographically
300 scale-up the assessments, at the level of an eco-region (Borja *et al.*, 2010). This means
301 that the GEnS assessments of the MS need to be comparable in order to enable
302 integrating their assessments into an ecoregion-wide assessment and to avoid cross-
303 border anomalies. This requires that comparable methods and aggregation rules are
304 needed to ensure minimum standards for GEnS reporting across MS and as such we
305 advocate a set of common principles (expanded from Claussen *et al.*, 2011):

- 306 (i) The integration across levels of different complexity should accommodate
307 different alternatives, i.e., integration below Descriptor level (across indicators
308 within criteria, and criteria within Descriptors) could certainly differ from
309 Descriptor level integration (see Table 3, for different options at this level);
- 310 (ii) Integrate across *state* Descriptors (D1, D3, D4, D6) differently than across
311 *pressure* Descriptors (D2, D5, D7, D8, D9, D10, D11) (see Table 1, for
312 identification);

313 (iii) Consider a different contribution of the two types of main Descriptors for the
314 overall GEnS evaluation – giving *state* Descriptors a higher weight, as receptors
315 of the impacts produced by pressures. The rationale for this, as recognized by
316 Claussen *et al.* (2011), is that “in principle, where GEnS for state-based
317 Descriptors (D1, 3, 4, 6) are achieved it follows that GEnS for pressure-based
318 Descriptors should also be met”; this makes the assumption that if the state is
319 satisfactory then the pressures must be having a limited (or mitigated) impact.

320

321 Independently of which aggregation proposal(s) is adopted and at which level,
322 the precautionary principle should always be observed in the absence of more robust
323 knowledge.

324

325 **Proposal of an operational definition of GEnS**

326 Elliott (2011) suggested that the only main aim in marine management is to
327 protect and maintain the natural ecological functioning and at the same time deliver the
328 benefits for society (based on ecosystem services and societal benefits) – this is de facto
329 the Ecosystem Approach. Hence, we suggest that this should be taken as a starting point
330 to define GEnS – in essence that GEnS is achieved if the conservation objectives, the
331 ecosystem services and the societal benefits are delivered sustainably. If this is accepted
332 then the challenge is to make this operational and indicate how it can be linked to
333 monitoring, management and spatial planning.

334 The essence of the GEnS concept is to determine what type of ecological change
335 is possible as the result of human pressures. If the primary aim is to ensure ‘healthy,
336 productive and safe seas’ then we could use the *7 indicators for general application* for
337 the diagnosis of ecosystem pathology proposed by Harding (1992; see also Elliott

338 2011): primary production, nutrients, species diversity and abiotic zones, instability and
339 biotic composition, disease prevalence, size spectrum, bioaccumulation (and effects) of
340 contaminants. Hence, an adverse change in any of these indicates a deviation from
341 GEnS and thus a reduction in health of the system (see Tett *et al.*, in press) – thus
342 equating GEnS with ‘healthy’. This also implies that a healthy system is robust to the
343 effects of stressors (Tett *et al.*, in press; Mouillot *et al.*, 2013).

344 If GEnS is regarded as being synonymous with naturally ‘productive’ then we
345 need to include the unifying currency for determining whether the marine system is
346 delivering what society wants (an anthropocentric view) (Atkins *et al.*, 2011a, 2011b).
347 That is, whether the seas are maintaining the ecosystem services and delivering societal
348 benefits (in a sustainable way). For example, if the marine system delivers the relevant
349 ecosystem services without compromising the natural ecosystem functioning then is that
350 sufficient to say an area is achieving GEnS? There can be also trade-offs between
351 ecosystem services: for example, a cold-water coral reef can provide high value for the
352 ‘regulation and maintenance service’ by for example providing the nursery function for
353 some fish species, and at the same time the ‘provisioning service’, the capture of wild
354 fish of other species is decreasing because of a legal regulation (e.g. establishment of
355 Marine Protected Area, or closure for deep water fisheries) (Foley *et al.*, 2010). In such
356 cases, there is the need to identify beneficiaries, and to evaluate how society, as a
357 whole, would benefit from protecting the reef. If only economic use values were used
358 then this emphasise an anthropocentric definition of GEnS, as above (i.e. ‘seas are
359 maintaining the ecosystem services and delivering societal benefits in a sustainable
360 way’) but we also have to incorporate the non-use values (Atkins *et al.*, 2011a). In
361 addition, this has to encompass the intrinsic conservation value, i.e. the value of the
362 ecosystem for its own sake (Pascual *et al.*, 2012).

363 We consider that the definition (or definitions) of GEnS not only has (or have)
364 to summarise the status but that they have to be able to be used in real-time assessments
365 and the operational management of the marine system. Therefore, the operational GEnS
366 definition that we propose is: “*GEnS is achieved when physico-chemical (including*
367 *contaminants, litter and noise) and hydrographical conditions are maintained at a level*
368 *where the structuring components of the ecosystem are present and functioning,*
369 *enabling the system to be resistant (ability to withstand stress) and resilient (ability to*
370 *recover after a stressor) to harmful effects of human pressures/activities/impacts, where*
371 *they maintain and provide the ecosystem services that deliver societal benefits in a*
372 *sustainable way (i.e. that pressures associated with uses cumulatively do not hinder the*
373 *ecosystem components in order to retain their natural diversity, productivity and*
374 *dynamic ecological processes, and where recovery is rapid and sustained if a use*
375 *ceases)”.*

376 The main challenge is to translate this definition into terms suitable to provide
377 an operational tool. Based on the previous section (integration of the assessments), we
378 propose that there are at least 8 options to determine the GEnS in a regional sea context
379 (Table 3). Hence, we detail the concept behind the options, then select the decision rule
380 for the method to be implemented, consider what type and amount of data are required,
381 and then consider the pros and cons of the different options. The options from 1 to 8 are
382 sequentially less demanding of new data, and the degree of detailed ecological
383 assessment. As such, Option 1, which is most similar to the WFD approach,
384 deconstructs GEnS into the 11 descriptors and then into the component indicators,
385 assessing each for each area before attempting to produce an overall assessment (Table
386 3). However, having a complete dataset covering all descriptors and indicators for the
387 assessment is difficult, and the use of pressure maps as a proxy of the status and impacts

388 to marine ecosystems could be considered (Aubry and Elliott, 2006; Halpern *et al.*,
389 2008; Korpinen *et al.*, 2012). Option 7, in contrast, only uses published data for the
390 activities, and then infers a relationship between activity, pressures and impacts both on
391 the natural and anthropogenic system. Between these extremes, there are several options
392 to integrate and present information (see Borja *et al.*, 2011; Halpern *et al.*, 2012), each
393 with its own requirements, pros and cons (Table 3). Most of the Options have been used
394 in quality assessments of estuaries, lagoons, coastal and marine areas (see Table 3
395 references).

396 Determining the quality of any ecological element (individual, community,
397 population or ecosystem), in relation to single or combined pressures and accounting for
398 the inherent variability in the system is expensive and, in the current economic climate,
399 this may be prohibitive (Borja and Elliott, 2013). Therefore, as suggested with Option 7,
400 it is likely to be easier and cheaper to determine the GENs as the ‘absence of pressures’
401 in a region rather than the ‘presence of good environment’. The former has been used to
402 good effect to create Quality Status Reports from OSPAR (2010) and HELCOM (2010)
403 and can be obtained from maps and aerial photos, databases of users, automatic
404 measuring such as Vessel Monitoring Systems (VMS) in the open sea, and limited
405 modelling exercises. In contrast, detecting the ‘presence of a good environment’
406 requires a large amount of monitoring, i.e. each ecological and physical component
407 needs to be assessed for its ‘goodness’, in itself a human (and thus subjective) construct
408 (Mee *et al.*, 2008). Despite this, detecting severe impacts is straightforward. However,
409 in most seas surrounding developed countries, these impacts are likely to be on a small
410 scale and/or produced by point-source pressures and thus controlled by licensing. This
411 leads to a problem of whether to judge the quality of a sea area according to the many
412 pressures which may each only affect a small area and cumulatively affect a small

413 proportion of a sea area but still resulting in a label of ‘Poor Environmental Status’.
414 Also this would require agreeing a pressure classification and indices that can show the
415 strength and spatial extent of, and time for exposure to the pressure (e.g. using a
416 pressure classification: low pressure, medium pressure, high pressure). For instance,
417 based on the WFD pressure data reported by MS, it is possible to present the percentage
418 of all classified water bodies affected by certain types of pressures (Solheim *et al.*,
419 2012). The pressures included in the assessment are point and/or diffuse pollution per
420 marine region, hydro-morphological pressures and/or altered habitats per marine region.
421 However, the intensity and extent of different pressures is not evaluated – only presence
422 or absence. As an example, the Baltic Sea Pressure Index (Korpinen *et al.*, 2012)
423 provides a dimensionless value of the indicator with a gradient from an absence of
424 pressures to cases (areas) where virtually almost all pressures are present. However, the
425 problem of boundary setting still remains including how to determine what is good and
426 what is not good (Mee *et al.*, 2008). One danger of focussing on pressures is that many
427 are point-source in nature and so trying to extrapolate to whole eco-regions and sub-
428 regions, as required by the MSFD, is difficult. Furthermore, diffuse sources may be
429 difficult to identify and tackle, especially if having a trans-boundary effect.

430 Option 5, suggesting the use of a tick-list approach, takes a quasi-legal approach
431 based on the probability of evidence, some or much of which may be based on informed
432 judgement or based on precedent elsewhere. For example, even if there are insufficient
433 data for all aspects, if the qualitative trends (even using expert judgement) in many of
434 the aspects all point to an area being in good status then by definition the area is in good
435 status (Ferreira *et al.*, 2011). This probability of evidence approach is used in common
436 law (i.e. as the best available evidence) and was the approach taken by Bricker *et al.*
437 (2003) to rigorously take ‘soft intelligence’ from many US estuaries relating to

438 eutrophication effects and combine this to form ‘hard data’, hence producing an
439 assessment which had the confidence of managers and stakeholders alike.

440 By definition, because of the way the MSFD has been constructed, GEnS
441 requires a multi-metric approach which can accommodate or encompass the descriptors
442 and component indicators/criteria. As suggested by Option 6, a bottom-up approach
443 whereby each is assessed and combined either numerically or, for example, as an
444 ‘amoeba-type’ representation (Ten Brink *et al.*, 1991), would be of value. Although
445 such a diagram, encompassing the descriptors, criteria and indicators, has not yet been
446 constructed, it is expected that it would indicate some kind of ecosystem ‘deformation’
447 from a circle or polygon or even the Ocean Health Index by Halpern *et al.* (2012). It is
448 especially important to incorporate and quantify the pressure and resilience directly into
449 an assessment, although this is always one of the most difficult aspects to achieve,
450 assuming this direct linkage and accounting for these “un-measurable” aspects.

451 The application of an operational definition of GEnS, such as that proposed
452 before, implies many challenges. Firstly, the current economic difficulties may preclude
453 an appropriate amount of monitoring to be carried out if any determination of GEnS
454 requires assessments for all descriptors and for all components and indicators of those
455 descriptors in all areas. Hence, the MSFD requires flexibility in selecting the most
456 relevant indicators and criteria. De Jonge *et al.* (2006) consider the problems of marine
457 monitoring against changing political imperatives, where the successive revision of
458 monitoring programmes usually equates to reductions, and Borja and Elliott (2013)
459 consider the problem of a lack of funding for monitoring and thus the potential threat of
460 uninformed marine decision-making. For example, the Danish national monitoring
461 programme was initiated in 1989 to follow responses in the aquatic environment to
462 nutrient reduction plans adopted in 1987 (Carstensen *et al.*, 2006). This monitoring

463 programme was ambitious from the outset but revisions have gradually reduced
464 monitoring efforts, and for the first WFD planning period (2009-2015) and with the
465 start of the MSFD monitoring (from 2014), the sampling effort is at its lowest for more
466 than two decades. Thus, we are concerned that the information base on which decision-
467 making should be made, potentially with large economic consequences, is gradually
468 eroding due to reduced budgets for marine monitoring.

469 Secondly, it is questioned whether there should be a continuing emphasis on the
470 physical and chemical approach against a prevailing desire (and philosophy) to monitor
471 ecological health. If there are accepted links between deterioration in physical and
472 chemical parameters and the reduction in ecological health then the former parameters
473 can be used as a proxy for the latter and may be easier to monitor. However, if such
474 links are not reliable then the more complex and expensive ecological monitoring will
475 be required. This also relates to the difficulty of determining and implementing what is
476 meant by pass and fail in an operational context, especially against a background of
477 high variability in all aspects of the biological, physical and chemical system in the
478 marine environment. The high variability may require ecologists to acknowledge that
479 some of the components cannot be used operationally in monitoring for good
480 environmental status, for example, trying to determine if a low and highly variable
481 abundance of a marine mammal conforms to an accepted level. Hence, as suggested
482 above, it may be easier to determine ‘an absence of pressures’ rather than a ‘presence of
483 good physical, chemical and biological features’ and rely on adequate, remotely
484 collected data and information.

485 In addition, further research is required to determine the relative merits of
486 measuring each ecological component, which are surrogates or proxies for others, in
487 which case is it better and more cost-effective to measure an absence of pressures rather

488 than a presence of good ecology, and which components are most suitable and cost-
489 effective to assess which pressure effects.

490 Thirdly, there are spatial considerations and anomalies including the problems
491 created by the overlap in space of the WFD, MSFD, Habitats Directive and the
492 proposed Maritime Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Management Directive, as
493 well as the Common Fisheries Policy. This also needs consideration of which piece of
494 legislation takes precedence in an area and so whether the definitions of ‘good status’,
495 GEnS, GEcS or FCS (Favourable Conservation Status, under the Habitats Directive),
496 are in agreement. It has been suggested that the WFD takes precedence in the near-shore
497 area and the Habitats Directive in designated areas of conservation. However, there are
498 likely to be spatial anomalies in the proposed system whereby marine areas may fail
499 under GEnS and yet still be given the status as Special Protection Areas (SPA) and
500 Special Areas for Conservation (SAC), under the Habitats and Wild Birds Directives.

501

502 **Concluding Remarks and Recommendations**

503 As discussed here: (i) marine management governance initiatives have to deal
504 with the complexity of the marine and adjoining systems and thus the initiatives become
505 complex in themselves, as with the WFD (Hering *et al.*, 2010); (ii) there is a plethora of
506 such mechanisms such as the Regional Seas Conventions (such as OSPAR, HELCOM),
507 which have been assessing and advising on marine areas since the 1970s, and (iii) it is
508 recognised that there is limited funding for large-scale data gathering exercises. Hence,
509 we advocate that the means of implementing the MSFD have to be simpler than the
510 WFD, to be based on the work of the Regional Seas Conventions and as much as
511 possible be based on existing datasets.

512 Above we propose an operational definition of GEnS and, based on the
513 collective experience of the authors, hope that this can be accepted even after being
514 refined as necessary. In order to be accepted there is the need to show that such a
515 definition encompasses all descriptors and their criteria, and that we are aware of the
516 data and information required (and either existing or which can be obtained) to ensure
517 the definition is met (see Figure 2). We have made a preliminary attempt at this in Table
518 4. This shows that whereas we have some data covering the regional seas, we have
519 many data based on pressures within small areas and so any large scale assessment will
520 have to be derived by combining such data. Hence, it illustrates the fundamental
521 challenge of arriving at a regional quality status either by having a broad approach and
522 omitting or down-weighting point-source problems or summing the point-source
523 problems (which may cover only a very small area) to indicate the quality status of the
524 whole area. Furthermore, in keeping with the overall direction of the MSFD, and indeed
525 the recently proposed Maritime Spatial Planning and Integrated Coastal Management
526 Directive (European Commission, 2013), we emphasise in the definition and Table 4
527 the need for the marine environment to not only protect and enhance the nature
528 conservation features but also to deliver ecosystem services and societal benefits.

529 While it is important to define what we mean by GEnS, Table 4 still emphasises
530 the challenge of having sufficient methods and measurements to indicate when it has
531 been achieved. While for certain elements we have a plethora of such agreed targets and
532 limits, for example the levels of contaminants that should not be exceeded in water and
533 seafood, for many others such limits are not yet defined. For example, while indicators
534 have been proposed for many ecosystem services and societal benefits (e.g. see the
535 review by Liqueste *et al.*, 2013), these are to indicate the direction of trajectories (i.e. is a

536 feature getting better or worse) rather than a level against which successful management
537 is judged.

538 Consequently, there are a number of research and management needs. As shown
539 here, there is a continuing and pressing need for scientists and policy makers to clarify
540 the terminology across the different policy drivers, e.g. GEnS in MSFD, Favourable
541 Conservation Status in the Habitats Directive, Good Ecological Status in the WFD,
542 Ecological Quality Objectives of OSPAR, or approaches within the Convention on
543 Biological Diversity. HELCOM (and OSPAR) has discussed this in detail (see
544 HELCOM (2013) TARGREV report).

545 The relationship between the implementation of the MSFD and integrated
546 maritime spatial planning is as yet poorly defined especially as much marine
547 management is sector-based. Hence there is the need to integrate the monitoring and
548 assessment across the policy drivers/descriptors, etc. It is necessary to assess the costs
549 and benefits of co-location of marine activities and their effect on attaining GEnS and
550 on the maintenance of ecosystem services and the delivery of societal benefits (Christie
551 *et al.*, in press). Thus, further research is required to produce a better understanding and
552 more comprehensive datasets but also to concentrate on processes and cause and effect
553 and to improve the science of monitoring especially to ask appropriate questions,
554 determine key processes and give an interaction of components and processes.

555 Whichever way is used to define GEnS it will require an assessment of change
556 against an expected standard or reference condition. While this has not yet been
557 determined, once GEnS is determined then such a reference-deviation will be required
558 as a management mechanism. However, given the difficulties of gathering data and the
559 cost of producing data-rich means for defining reference conditions (i.e. comparisons
560 with natural areas, hindcasting and predictive models), in the first instance reliance on

561 expert judgement will be needed (Borja *et al.*, 2012). An expert system that can capture
562 expert judgement in a robust and defensible manner, as demonstrated across different
563 continents (Teixeira *et al.*, 2010), may be required.

564 As shown here and elsewhere, there is a plethora of indicators and targets and it
565 is likely to be exceedingly difficult to reconcile the use of all of these, especially across
566 the 11 descriptors—and it may well be unnecessary. They respond differently both in
567 time and space, and might be counter-acting; although they may indicate poor quality in
568 a small area, they will be absorbed across larger spatial scales and thus have little
569 influence in an overall good quality eco-region. Consequently, we take the view that a
570 combination of quantitative indicator targets and, where these are lacking, expert
571 judgement are needed to integrate the natural and social science requirements for the
572 sound implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

573

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581

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Table 1. Qualitative descriptors, criteria and indicators, selected by the European Commission (2010), and to be used in the assessment of the environmental status of marine waters, in the context of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive.

DESCRIPTOR	CRITERIA	INDICATOR		
1: Biological diversity	1.1 Species distribution	1.1.1 Distributional range 1.1.2 Distributional pattern within the latter 1.1.3 Area covered by the species (for sessile/benthic species)		
	1.2 Population size	1.2.1 Population abundance and/or biomass		
	1.3 Population condition	1.3.1 Population demographic characteristics 1.3.2 Population genetic structure		
	1.4 Habitat distribution	1.4.1 Distributional range 1.4.2 Distributional pattern		
	1.5 Habitat extent	1.5.1 Habitat area 1.5.2 Habitat volume, where relevant		
	1.6 Habitat condition	1.6.1 Condition of the typical species and communities 1.6.2 Relative abundance and/or biomass, as appropriate 1.6.3 Physical, hydrological and chemical conditions		
	1.7 Ecosystem structure	1.7.1 Composition and relative proportions of ecosystem components (habitats, species)		
	2: Non-indigenous species	2.1 Abundance and state of non-indigenous species, in particular invasive species	2.1.1 Trends in abundance, temporal occurrence and spatial distribution of non-indigenous species	
		2.2 Environmental impact of invasive non-indigenous sp.	2.2.1 Ratio between invasive non-indigenous species and native species 2.2.2 Impacts of non-indigenous invasive species at the level of species, habitats and ecosystem	
	3: Exploited fish and shellfish	3.1 Level of pressure of the fishing activity	3.1.1 Fishing mortality (F) 3.1.2 Catch/biomass ratio	
		3.2 Reproductive capacity of the stock	3.2.1 Spawning Stock Biomass (SSB) 3.2.2 Biomass indices	
		3.3 Population age and size distribution	3.3.1 Proportion of fish larger than the mean size of first sexual maturation 3.3.2 Mean maximum length across all species found in research vessel surveys 3.3.3 95 % percentile of the fish length distribution observed in research vessel surveys 3.3.4 Size at first sexual maturation	
		4: Food webs	4.1 Productivity of key species or trophic groups	4.1.1 Performance of key predator species using their production per unit biomass
			4.2 Proportion of selected species at the top of food webs	4.2.1 Large fish (by weight)

	4.3 Abundance/distribution of key trophic groups/species	4.3.1 Abundance trends of functionally important selected groups/species
5: Human-induced eutrophication	5.1. Nutrients levels	5.1.1 Nutrients concentration in the water column 5.1.2 Nutrient ratios (silica, nitrogen and phosphorus)
	5.2 Direct effects of nutrient enrichment	5.2.1 Chlorophyll concentration in the water column 5.2.2. Water transparency related to increase in suspended algae 5.2.3 Abundance of opportunistic macroalgae 5.2.4 Species shift in floristic composition such as diatom to flagellate ratio, benthic to pelagic shifts, as well as bloom events of nuisance/toxic algal blooms caused by human activities
	5.3 Indirect effects of nutrient enrichment	5.3.1 Abundance of perennial seaweeds and seagrasses impacted by decrease in water transparency 5.3.2 Dissolved oxygen changes and size of the area concerned
	6.1 Physical damage, having regard to substrate characteristics	6.1.1 Type, abundance, biomass and areal extent of relevant biogenic substrate 6.1.2 Extent of the seabed significantly affected by human activities for the different substrate types
	6.2 Condition of benthic community	6.2.1 Presence of particularly sensitive and/or tolerant species 6.2.2 Multi-metric indices assessing benthic community condition and functionality, such as species diversity and richness, proportion of opportunistic to sensitive species 6.2.3 Proportion of biomass or number of individuals in the macrobenthos above specified length/size 6.2.4 Parameters describing the characteristics of the size spectrum of the benthic community
	6: Seafloor integrity	
7: Hydrographical conditions	7.1 Spatial characterisation of permanent alterations	7.1.1 Extent of area affected by permanent alterations
	7.2 Impact of permanent hydrographical changes	7.2.1 Spatial extent of habitats affected by the permanent alteration 7.2.2 Changes in habitats, in particular the functions provided due to altered hydrographical conditions
8: Contaminants	8.1 Concentration of contaminants	8.1.1 Concentration of the contaminants measured in matrices such as biota, sediment and water
	8.2 Effects of contaminants	8.2.1 Levels of pollution effects on the ecosystem components concerned, having regard to the selected biological processes and taxonomic groups where a cause/effect relationship has been established 8.2.2 Occurrence, origin, extent of significant acute pollution events and their impact on biota physically affected by this pollution
9: Contaminants in fish and seafood	9.1 Levels, number and frequency of contaminants	9.1.1 Actual levels of contaminants that have been detected and number of contaminants which have exceeded maximum regulatory levels 9.1.2 Frequency of regulatory levels being exceeded
	10.1 Characteristics of litter in the marine and coastal environment	10.1.1 Trends in the amount of litter washed ashore and/or deposited on coastlines, including analysis of its composition, spatial distribution and source 10.1.2 Trends in the amount of litter in the water column and deposited on the seafloor 10.1.3 Trends in the amount, distribution and composition of micro-particles
10: Litter		

	10.2 Impacts of litter on marine life	10.2.1 Trends in the amount and composition of litter ingested by marine animals
11: Energy and noise	11.1 Distribution in time and place of loud, low and mid frequency impulsive sounds	11.1.1 Proportion of days and their distribution within a calendar year over areas of a determined surface, as well as their spatial distribution, in which anthropogenic sound sources exceed levels that are likely to entail significant impact
	11.2 Continuous low frequency sound	11.2.1 Trends in the ambient noise level within the 1/3 octave bands 63 and 125 Hz (centre frequency) measured by observation stations and/or with the use of models

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811 Table 2. Normative definition of Good Environmental Status as suggested by Task Groups for each descriptor and modified from Cardoso *et al.*
 812 (2010). Key: OAO: ‘one out, all out’ principle; GEnS: good environmental status; IAS: Invasive alien species; NIS: non-indigenous
 813 species; EnQS: Environmental Quality Standards; MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

DESCRIPTOR	GOOD ENVIRONMENTAL STATUS DEFINITION	AGGREGATION RULES
1: Biological diversity	GEnS will be achieved if there is no further loss of the diversity of genes, species and habitats/communities at ecologically relevant scales and when deteriorated components, where intrinsic environmental conditions allow, are restored to target levels. Target levels are defined as being such that “the quality and occurrence of habitats and the distribution and abundance of species are in line with prevailing physiographic, geographic and climatic conditions”. Some deviation from reference conditions, as a result of human use of the marine environment, is acceptable, providing the terms of the Descriptor are still met.	GEnS will be achieved when each of the targets established by the Member States for all the attributes and components of biological diversity have been met (OOAO)
2: Non-indigenous species	IAS cause adverse effects on environmental quality resulting from changes in biological, chemical and physical properties of aquatic ecosystems. These changes include, but are not limited to: elimination or extinction of sensitive and/or rare populations; alteration of native communities; algal blooms; modification of substrate conditions and the shore zones; alteration of oxygen and nutrient content, pH and transparency of water; accumulation of synthetic pollutants, etc. The magnitude of impacts may vary from low to massive and they can be sporadic, short-term or permanent. The degradation gradient in relation to NIS is a function of their relative abundances and distribution ranges, which may vary from low abundances in one locality with no measurable adverse effects up to occurrence in high numbers in many localities, causing massive impact on native communities, habitats and ecosystem functioning.	Methods for aggregating indicators for GEnS assessments need to take into account the known IAS effects in other world regions or in neighbouring areas.
3: Exploited fish and shellfish	Since there is broad scientific evidence that GEnS cannot be achieved for all stocks simultaneously, a realistic threshold for the proportion of stocks with GEnS needs to be established above which the descriptor has achieved GEnS.	GEnS is achieved for a particular stock only if criteria for all attributes are fulfilled (OOAO).
4: Food webs	GEnS should ensure that populations of selected food web components occur at levels that are within acceptable ranges that will secure their long-term viability.	GEnS will therefore be achieved when the indicators describing the various attributes of the descriptor reach the thresholds set for them (OOAO)
5: Human-induced eutrophication	GEnS has been achieved when the biological community remains well-balanced and retains all necessary functions in the absence of undesirable disturbance associated with eutrophication (e.g. excessive algal blooms, low dissolved oxygen, declines in seagrasses, kills of benthic organisms and/or fish) and/or where there are no nutrient-related impacts on sustainable use of ecosystem goods and services.	No specific method is recommended, but those used must be robust, integrated, sufficiently sensitive, comparable, and with recognized scientific merit.

6: Seafloor integrity	The standard for GEnS should reflect the goals for management of the impacts of human activities on the sea floor. It is explicit in the definition of the descriptor that human uses of the ocean, including uses that affect the sea floor, are consistent with the MSFD, as long as those uses are sustainable. Sustainability is achieved when the pressures associated with all those uses cumulatively do not hinder the ecosystem components to retain their natural diversity, productivity and dynamic ecological processes. Perturbations due to use must be small enough that recovery is rapid and secure if a use ceases.	No single algorithm for combining indicator values will be appropriate for evaluating GEnS or providing a meaningful index of GEnS. It may be possible to conduct such analytical syntheses of Indicators for individual attributes on local scales. However, across attributes and on even moderate scales expert assessments rather than algorithmic formulae will be needed for evaluation.
8: Contaminants	Achievement of EnQS. Biological effects should be assessed against threshold levels of response that are indicative of significant harm to the organisms concerned.	Integration is greatly facilitated by coherent and consistent sets of assessment thresholds (EnQS).
9: Contaminants in fish and seafood	GEnS would be achieved if all contaminants are at levels below the levels established for human consumption or showing a downward trend (for the substances for which monitoring is ongoing but for which levels have not yet been set). However, it is generally felt that GEnS for descriptor 9 must be judged in view out the monitoring of descriptor 8, also dealing with contaminants in marine environment	OOAO
10: Litter	Definitions of the acceptable levels of harm and GEnS must consider impacts as assessed by the amount of litter in different compartments of the marine environment (seabed, sea surface, water column, coastline), ecological effects of the litter (e.g. plastics ingested by marine organisms; entanglement rates) and problems associated with degradation of litter (microparticles) as well as social and economic aspects. Tourism is strongly negatively affected by the presence of litter. An overriding objective will be a measurable and significant decrease (e.g. 10%/year for litter on coastlines) in the total amount of litter in the environment by 2020.	No proposal
11: Energy and noise	GEnS occurs when there is no adverse effect of energy inputs on any component of the marine environment. However, such an objective is probably not achievable if, for instance, behavioural disturbance or mortality of plankton (including planktonic larvae) is considered an adverse effect. Such an objective is probably not also measurable for a very large proportion of organisms in the marine environment.	No proposal

814 Table 3. Options for determining if an area/regional sea is in Good Environmental Status. Key: OOA: ‘one out, all out’ principle.

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Option	Decision rule	Data requirements	Pros	Cons	Examples in place
<i>Either:</i> 1. fulfilling all the indicators in all the descriptors	All indicators are met irrespective of weighting (OOA)	Data needed for all aspects on regional seas scale	Most comprehensive approach	Unreasonable data requirements; all areas will fail on at least one indicator; may include double-counting	None
<i>Or:</i> 2. fulfilling the indicators in all descriptors but as a weighted list according to the hierarchy of the descriptors	Agreeing the weighting	Data needed for all aspects on regional seas scale	Reflects the interlinked nature of the descriptors and avoids double counting	Unreasonable data requirements; problem of agreeing the weighting	HELCOM (2010); Borja <i>et al.</i> (2011); Aubry and Elliott (2006)
<i>Or:</i> 3. fulfilling the indicators just for the biodiversity descriptor and making sure these encompass all other quality changes	All biodiversity indicators are met irrespective of weighting	Data needed for all components of biodiversity	Focuses on the main aspect	Assumes that the biodiversity descriptor really does encompass all others	None
<i>Or:</i> 4. create a synthesis indicator which takes the view that 'GEnS is the ability of an area to support ecosystem services, produce societal benefits and still maintain and protect the conservation features'	Integration of the information from different descriptors and indicators, and evaluation of the overall benefits	Data needed for the indicators included in that synthesis indicator, valuation of the ecosystem services and benefits	Fulfils the main aim of marine management (see text)	Requires a new indicator and an agreement in the way of integrate the information; trade-offs between ecosystem services and their beneficiaries require either economic, ethical or political evaluation and decision, and cannot be based only on ecological knowledge	Borja <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Or:</i> 5. have a check-list (ticking boxes) of all the aspects needed	then if an area has e.g. more than 60% of the boxes ticked then it is in GEnS	An expert judgement approach, based on 'probability of evidence'	It may reflect the state of the science; if done rigorously then it may be the easiest to implement	It may be too subjective (i.e. based on soft intelligence)	Bricker <i>et al.</i> (1999); Ferreira <i>et al.</i> (2011)
<i>Or:</i> 6. have a summary diagram such as a spiders-web diagram	The shape of the diagram		Easy to understand and show to managers	The decision on when GEnS is achieved	Halpern <i>et al.</i> (2012)

showing the 'shape of GENs according to several headline indicators'					
<i>Or:</i> 7. not reporting the environmental status but only the list of pressures (i.e. on the premise that if an area has no obvious pressures then any changes in the area must be due to natural changes which are outside the control of management)	No pressures in an area sufficient to cause adverse effects	Quantitative maps of pressures	Can be derived by national databases, mapping, pressure lists	Relates to 'cause' rather than 'effect', difficult to set boundaries between pressure status classes: is it sufficient to base the assessment on the list of pressures, while those can have very different spatial extent and strength?	Aubry and Elliott (2006); Halpern <i>et al.</i> (2008); Korpinen <i>et al.</i> (2012) See also Solheim <i>et al.</i> (2012) for the analysis of WFD pressures and impacts
<i>Or:</i> 8. a combination of all/some of these when there are insufficient data in some areas or for some descriptors or indicators		Combination of pressures and descriptors data	Information available from Member States reports	Either requires too much information (hence unreasonable) or too little (hence inaccurate)	None

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819 Table 4. The operational basis of the proposed Good Environmental Status (GEnS) definition. Key: RSC: Regional Sea Conventions; VMS:
820 Vessel Monitoring System; EUNIS: European Nature Information System; WFD: Water Framework Directive; UWWTD: Urban and Waste
821 Water Treatment Directive; QSR: quality status reports from RSC; UKNEA: UK National Ecosystem Assessment; TEEB: The Economics of
822 Ecosystems and Biodiversity; CBD: CBD: Convention on Biological Diversity.
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<i>'GEnS is achieved when</i>	Related to which Descriptor?	How is this determined?	What data/information are available?	Which targets or limits to be used?
<i>.....physicochemical (including contaminants, litter and noise)</i>	5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11	Rapid assessment of pressures using GIS and presented via interactive .pdf documents; traditional sampling, buoys (different sensors, including acoustic)	Use of RSC databases to indicate the quality status of the area (using QSR), summed point-source inputs of contaminants; use of VMS for open sea fishing pressure; RSC eutrophication maps	Targets established in ad-hoc Directives (e.g. UWWTD, WFD, Environmental Quality Standards Directive, etc.) or RSC
<i>.....and hydrographical conditions are maintained at a level</i>	1, 6, 7	Remote measurements and aerial/satellite sensing; habitat surveys; traditional sampling	Seabed maps of selected areas, modelling of current patterns, satellite data for surface conditions (waves, currents, temperature, etc).	RSC, expert judgment
<i>.....where the structuring components of the ecosystem are present and functioning,</i>	1,3, 4, 6	Habitat maps, habitat suitability modelling, genomics, traditional sampling, abundance estimates of key species disparate survey data combined to give larger assessments; assessments and indices of biological functioning (productivity, competition, bioengineers, etc)	Broad biotope data (EUNIS), regional characterisation from summed local surveys; mammal and bird recording systems; fish stock assessments; specific surveys of ecosystem functioning supported by literature from elsewhere	Habitats and Birds Directives targets; Common Fisheries Policy Targets; expert judgement
<i>.....enabling the system to be resistant (ability to withstand stress) and resilient (ability to recover after a stressor) to harmful effects of human pressures/activities/impacts,</i>	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8	Multimetric indices, functional indices, size-spectra analyses; evidence of areas or components which have recovered after stressors have been removed	National and RSC databases Evidence from case-studies and Environmental Impact Assessments and extrapolated to wider areas; Alien and invasive species databases	Adapted targets from other directives (e.g. WFD) or RSC; expert judgement
<i>.....where they maintain and provide the ecosystem services</i>	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7,	An analysis of ecosystem services across sea areas, Contingency valuation,	A modelling and linked GIS analysis of habitats and ecosystems to ecosystem services will be needed; data and information from QSR	None available; some indicators of trends (e.g. UKNEA, TEEB, CBD reports) but not of targets

		biological valuation and other economic valuation techniques		(see Liqueste <i>et al.</i> , 2013)
<i>.....that deliver societal benefits</i>	3, 4, 5, 9,	Economic valuation techniques	Fisheries statistics, monitoring of seafood quality, Databases of human uses; fisheries (VMS data), oil & gas, aggregate returns, etc;	Legal limits for contaminants in seafood, fish stocks under safe limits, seabed extraction within permits, etc.
<i>.....in a sustainable way (i.e. that pressures associated with uses cumulatively do not hinder the ecosystem components) in order to retain their natural diversity, productivity and dynamic ecological processes,</i>	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	Productivity values and separation of natural from anthropogenic production; alien and introduced species are minimised	National and RSC databases; use of data from small areas extrapolated to larger areas; Alien and Invasive species databases.	Legal limits for contaminants in seafood, fish stocks under safe limits; expert judgement
<i>..... and where recovery is rapid and sustained if a use ceases'.</i>	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11	Traditional sampling, trend analysis, Evidence of areas or components which have recovered after stressors have been removed	Long-term monitoring series; Alien and Invasive species databases.	Trends showing a tendency towards the previous state (before pressure) (i.e. hindcasting)

825 Figure captions

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827 Figure 1: The indicative list of 12 characteristics of environmental targets as outlined in
828 Annex IV Marine Strategy Framework Directive (modified from Claussen *et al.*
829 (2011)).

830 Figure 2: Making operational the definition of Good Environmental Status. QSR:
831 Quality Standard Reports

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